

PREPARATION OF SOME NEW ACID HYDRAZIDES AND HYDRAZONES

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The preparation of the hydrazides of malonanilic, malon-*o*-, -*m*- and -*p*-toluidic, and malon-*o*-, -*m*- and -*p*-chloroanilic acids is described. Malon-*o*-chloroanilic acid hydrazide has been used to prepare the corresponding hydrazones from various aldehydes and ketones.

Acid hydrazides find considerable use in chemotherapy, and such compounds in large number have been prepared and their properties investigated by earlier workers. Yale *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1933) have described the preparation of a number of new hydrazides, but their emphasis has been on the isonicotinic acid hydrazide type, with a view to establishing the structural requirements for antituberculous activity.

This communication deals with the preparation of the hydrazides of a number of malonic acid derivatives, and the use of one of these for the preparation of hydrazones from aldehydes and ketones. Malonanilic acid, the three malontoluidic acids, and the three malonchloroanilic acids have been chosen for this purpose. The ethyl esters of these acids were prepared by a slight modification of the method described by Chattaway and Olmsted (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 940). The ethyl esters of malon-*o*- and -*m*-chloroanilic acids have been isolated in pure condition for the first time. The other esters were prepared by earlier workers.

The method employed for the preparation of the acid hydrazides is more or less the same as the one adopted by Yale *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The yield m.p., etc. of the hydrazides obtained are shown in Table I.

Further investigations show that these acid hydrazides can be used as reagents for detection of carbonyl compounds. These readily form crystalline hydrazones with a number of aldehydes and ketones. Several hydrazones were prepared using malon-*o*-chloroanilic acid hydrazide. The general procedure has been to take equimolecular quantities of the aldehyde or ketone and the acid hydrazide in ethanolic solution, and to keep the mixture at room temperature for 15 to 30 minutes. In the case of chloral it was observed that in ethanolic solution the product formed had a nitrogen content higher than what was expected, and it melted with decomposition at 221°. The identity of the compound could not be established. When dry benzene was used in place of ethanol and the mixture refluxed for 30 minutes, the expected hydrazone crystallised out. The m.p., yield, etc. of the hydrazones are recorded in Table II.

The ketones were slower to react than the aldehydes. Under the conditions tried, *n*-heptaldehyde, 5-nitrothiophen-2-aldehyde, acetone and benzophenone did not react.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl. Malon-o-chloroanilate.—A mixture of *o*-chloroaniline (5 g.) and ethyl malonate (10 g.) was refluxed for 30 minutes in a r.b. flask fitted with an air condenser of such a length that the ethanol formed could escape, allowing ethyl malonate to flow back into the flask. The contents were allowed to cool, ethanol (30 c.c.) added, and the crystals of malon-di-*o*-chloroanilide separating were filtered off. The filtrate containing malon-*o*-chloroanilate was added slowly with stirring to 500 c.c. of water. The ester, which was precipitated as a pale yellow solid, was filtered off and recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colorless crystals, m.p. 60°, yield 3.5 g. (36.8%). (Found : N, 5.38. $C_{11}H_{13}O_3NCl$ requires N, 5.79%).

Similarly ethyl malonanilate (m.p. 39°, yield 40%), ethyl malon-*o*-toluidate (m.p. 73°, yield 13.2%), ethyl malon-*p*-toluidate (m.p. 85°, yield 44.7%), ethyl malon-*m*-chloroanilate (m.p. 74°, yield 31.6%; found : N, 6.13; $C_{11}H_{13}O_3NCl$ requires N, 5.79%), and ethyl malon-*p*-chloroanilate (m.p. 92-94°, yield 44.7%) were prepared. Ethyl malon-*m*-toluidate was obtained as a viscous liquid, and this was found pure enough for the subsequent step. Other esters were prepared as above.

Malon-o-chloroanilic Acid Hydrazide.—85% Hydrazine hydrate (1 c.c.) was added to a solution of ethyl malon-*o*-chloroanilate (2 g.) in ethanol (5 c.c.). The reaction was spontaneous. The contents became slightly warm and the hydrazide crystallised out in colorless needles. The flask was set aside for 30 minutes. The solid mass was dissolved in hot ethanol (20 c.c.) and this on cooling deposited pure crystals of malon-*o*-chloroanilic acid hydrazide, m.p. 128°, yield 1.53 g. (81.2%). Other hydrazides were prepared similarly.

The purification of malonanilic acid hydrazide and malon-*m*-toluidic acid hydrazide was tedious. These could, however, be obtained pure by repeated extraction with boiling water in which the hydrazides are soluble.

TABLE I
New acid hydrazides.

Compounds.	M. P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
Malonanilic X*	186°	67.0%	$C_9H_{11}O_2N_2$	22.23	21.76
Malon- <i>o</i> -toluidic X	136°	66.19	$C_{10}H_{13}O_2N_2$	19.90	20.29
Malon- <i>m</i> -toluidic X	168°	35.02	$C_{10}H_{13}O_2N_2$	20.40	20.29
Malon- <i>p</i> -toluidic X	182°	64.60	$C_{10}H_{13}O_2N_2$	19.92	20.29
Malon- <i>o</i> -chloroanilic X	128°	81.21	$C_9H_{10}O_2N_2Cl$	18.49	18.49
Malon- <i>m</i> -chloroanilic X	179°	87.20	$C_9H_{10}O_2N_2Cl$	19.16	18.49
Malon- <i>p</i> -chloroanilic X	188°	66.34	$C_9H_{10}O_2N_2Cl$	18.64	18.49

*X stands for acid hydrazide.

TABLE II
New hydrazones.

Hydrazone.	M. P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
Furfuraldehyde-R*	196°	88.4%	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	14.01	13.74
Thiophen-2-aldehyde-R	168°	49.1	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	13.62	13.06
Chloral-R	178°	27.6	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₄	11.82	11.76
Benzaldehyde-R	193°	86.5	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	13.02	13.31
<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde-R	208°	93.6	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	11.93	12.00
5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde-R	213°	87.0	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	11.21	11.48
5-Bromosalicylaldehyde-R	218°	99.7	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ ClBr	10.69	10.23
3:5-Dibromosalicylaldehyde-R	214	82.7	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ ClBr ₂	9.04	8.58
3:5-Diiodosalicylaldehyde-R	221°	81.1	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ ClI ₂	7.33	7.19
3-Nitrosalicylaldehyde-R	206°	92.4	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	14.83	14.87
5 Nitrosalicylaldehyde-R	222°	83.4	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	15.14	14.87
3:5-Dinitrosalicylaldehyde-R	208°	85.7	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	16.84	16.61
3-Nitro-5-chlorosalicylaldehyde-R	210°	94.4	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	13.05	13.62
3-Nitro-5-bromosalicylaldehyde-R	204°	88.8	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ ClBr	12.36	12.29
Salicylaldehyde-R	199°	89.8	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	12.44	12.67
Methylethyl ketone-R	150°	44.5	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	15.32	14.90
Acetophenone-R	191°	61.5	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	12.66	12.75

*R stands for malon-*o*-chloroanilic acid hydrazone.

Hydrazones.—In the case of liquid aldehydes, the acid hydrazide was dissolved in the minimum quantity of cold ethanol and an equimolecular quantity of the aldehyde was added. The mixture was kept aside for about 30 minutes, and then the hydrazone separating was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

In the case of solid aldehydes, the acid hydrazide and the aldehyde were taken in ethanol and warmed till a homogeneous solution was obtained. It was set aside and extracted as before.

In the case of ketones, the mixture was refluxed for 1-2 hours.